

USING DIFFERENT MEDIATIONS TO FOSTER THE DEVELOPMENT OF RELATIVISTIC ZONE IN CONCEPTUAL PROFILE OF REFERENCE FRAME

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The importance of Modern Physics themes in basic education is recognized. However, as these are complex issues, it is necessary to develop and use resources that can facilitate its learning. In this way, this research relates the use of four different resources that use, each, the four levels of mediation according to the Cognitive Networks Mediation Theory (CNMT) to facilitate the development of the relativistic zone in the conceptual profile of reference frame for understanding the Special Relativity Theory (SRT) by high school students. The results obtained indicate that the use of different mediations, especially hypercultural mediation, can contribute to the construction of mental images and then the development of this conceptual profile zone.

Keywords: Special Relativity; Conceptual Profile; CNMT.

INTRODUCTION

Modern Physics knowledge is of great relevance in the context of basic education. These topics are crucial for a better understanding of the current world since most of the emerging technologies are explained by them. One of the cornerstones of Modern Physics is undoubtedly Einstein's Special Relativity Theory (SRT), through which the emergence of the largely used technology, of the *Global Positioning System* (GPS) was made possible. However, it is a complex theory, which requires a high level of abstraction for its understanding,

Moreover, as relativistic effects are imperceptible in everyday life, students tend to believe that any changes in time intervals or size of objects for different reference frames are related to perception, optical illusions, or measurement failure, believing that relativity is not a real phenomenon (Kim & Kim, 2011). Among the main difficulties presented by students, imagining the relativistic situations seems to be of critical importance (Ünlü Yavas & Kizilcik, 2016) and the acceptance of the consequences of the SRT, such as time dilation and space contraction (Dimitriadi & Halkia, 2012; Velentzas & Halkia, 2013). There is also a difficulty with the exchange of reference frame, which causes difficulties in understanding SRT (Gousopoulos, Kapotis, & Kalkanis, 2015).

Conceptual Profile

These obstacles to learning Special Relativity Theory may be associated with the lack of development of new regions in the conceptual profile. The idea of a conceptual profile brought up by Mortimer (1995) explains why certain misconceptions remain in the student's cognitive structure, even after he/she has learned new scientific concepts. Mortimer defines his idea of conceptual profile as “a model to describe changes in individual thoughts as a result of the teaching process” (Mortimer, 1995, p. 6).

According to Mortimer, the profile of a concept has different regions with increasingly explanatory ranges that carry both epistemological and ontological differences. Therefore, during the teaching-learning

process of a concept, new regions of its conceptual profile are developed. It is important that the student learns how to carry over these regions of the profile to use the more suitable definition for each situation.

Since SRT brought deep changes in the nature description, even though the student comprehends correctly Newtonian Physics, it is necessary to develop new regions in the conceptual profile to understand SRT. A crucial concept regarding the theory is of reference frame, therefore, in order to student comprehend it, it is necessary that he/she develops a new region on reference frame's conceptual profile. Ayala Filho and Frezza (2007) constructed a conceptual profile for the concept of 'reference frame' containing three different zones: *the common sense*, *Newtonian Physics*, and *the relativistic zone*. Therefore, the student must develop a 'relativistic zone' in his/her conceptual profile of reference frame.

Cognitive Networks Mediation Theory

Seeking to stimulate the development of the relativistic zone of the conceptual profile of reference frame, different types of mediations, according to the Cognitive Networks Mediation Theory (CNMT) (Souza, Silva, Silva, Roazzi, & Carrilho, 2012) can be used during the activities with students. According to the theory, the human brain naturally uses external organized resources to complement and expand its natural, biologic, information processing capacity. Moreover, the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) has caused changes in cognitive structure of individuals.

So, the interaction with external resources takes place through essentially four different levels: psychophysical mediation, with the use of physical objects, stimulating sensorimotor schemes; social mediation, through interaction between individuals in a group, it can occur directly or indirectly; cultural mediation, using symbolic schemes, such as language; and *hypercultural* mediation, which occurs using technological tools, as ICT.

In the process of interaction with the external resources, new internal features are developed, called *drivers*. These drivers act as "virtual machines" (Souza & Roazzi, 2009) and translate inputs and outputs between the brain and the external resource. Therefore, the usage of different mediations could stimulate the development of new regions in the conceptual profile, specially the *hypercultural* mediation dealing with SRT, as found in previous studies (Souza & Serrano, 2020).

Research Question

Considering the theoretical background presented here, the present research relied on the use of the four types of mediations when dealing with SRT with third-year high school students from a public school in Brazil aiming to stimulate the development of a relativistic zone in conceptual profile of reference frame. Our research question is "What levels of mediations are more effective to facilitate the development of the relativistic zone of the conceptual profile of reference frame?", we sought not only to investigate whether students were able to develop the relativistic zone of the conceptual profile of reference frame after the activities, but also which mediations were most effective in this process.

METHODOLOGY

The present research was developed with 82 students of the third year of high school from a public school in Brazil, during the curricular classes of Physics. The activities were carried out in the second half of 2019, so before the Covid-19 pandemic, using the four levels of mediation during the SRT approach.

Therefore, a presentation of 63 slides¹ (containing images, videos, and animated gifs), a questionnaire² for being used as pre-test and post-test, two mock-ups and two computer simulations³ were developed.

During the activities with students, social mediation occurred through the interaction with the teacher (as the teacher explained using speech, gestures and the chalkboard both temporal expansion and spatial contraction) and between students during activities; cultural mediation was used by watching videos explaining relativistic models; psychophysical mediation, occurred with the use of models representing the space-time diagrams for relativity by the mock-ups; and, finally, *hypercultural* mediation occurred with the use of computer simulations by the students, representing time expansion and space contraction.

Figure 1. Computer simulations showing space contraction (above) and time dilation (below).

The students answered the pre-test and post-test questionnaires immediately before and after the activities. The researchers analysed all answers to both the pre-test and post-test and selected a subset of 14 students to be interviewed. The interviews were conducted by the teacher-researcher individually through the *Report Aloud* protocol (Trevisan, Serrano, Wolff, & Ramos, 2019), by a constant dialogue between interviewer and interviewee, while the student explains what he/she thought and of what he/she remembered during the activities developed.

All interviews were recorded on video and transcribed for the analysis carried out through Depictive Gestural Analysis (Clement & Stephens, 2010; Monaghan & Clement, 1999), looking for the connection between the depictive gestures performed by students and their mental images, as well as investigating the origin of these images. These gestures can be considered a parallel “speech” that happens while the verbal speech is made, allowing the identification of mental simulations used during the activities.

¹ Available in: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1F1TqAjsVc7Ovj7Vle9YObg4kAIUGmsnr?usp=sharing>

² Available in: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/11gkBQaHKsV2La1QVIZ2w06ALUv16mf7j?usp=sharing>

³ Available in: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1sMg20libFq6urAUtL3e0b1xZdHy-cIB3?usp=sharing>

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Among the students interviewed, there are signs of the development of the relativistic zone of the conceptual profile of reference frame in four students: A14, A15, A18 and D23. These students showed a good comprehension of Special Relativity Theory considering the space contraction and time dilation as real phenomena. All four students also showed evidence of similar mental simulations for relativistic situations during the interviews, precisely for situations involving space contraction. The following are excerpts from the interviews where the four students showed evidences which suggest the development of the relativistic zone of the conceptual profile of reference frame after the activities developed.

Regarding the phenomenon of space contraction, there were two questions on tests dealing with the same situation: two trucks, one at rest in relation to the ground and the other getting close to it. The question 1 asked about the measured distance between the trucks when the moving truck has the speed 80 km/h and question 3 when it moves at $0.7c$. When talking about these questions, the four students demonstrated to understand that this phenomenon is real, as well as its relationship with the speed of the reference frame. These excerpts are presented below.

Student A14

When explaining the answers to the questions of the test, student A14 states that the distance measured by the reference frame of the moving truck would be “less than 100 m” due to its speed:

[13:34] A14: [...] I think it would be less than 100 m. Being at a very high speed, I think that here I got a little confused. Yeah, I think I got confused. Now seeing better, I think it is less than 100 m.

E: And when you think about [it] being smaller, what image comes to mind, what do you remember?

A14: Ah, I don't know, I can't imagine a truck at that speed, but I imagine, I don't know, like a [#FOG 14:13] rocket, something like that, it's very fast.

It is important to note that the student treated the difference as real, as she said, “it is less than 100 m” and not that the distance “seems smaller” (like other interviewed students declared). This acceptance suggests the existence of a new region on the conceptual profile of reference frame, which treats the space as a relative physical quantity.

Student A14 also performed the static depictive gesture #FOG when talked about a imagined rocket in this situation. The slides used during activities presented some animated gifs with rockets and ships. Possibly, the rocket remembered by the student is an internal resource, a static mental image, constructed by the interaction with this mediation.

Figure 2. The static gesture #FOG performed by student A14.

This internal resource helped the student to comprehend SRT and, possibly, supported the develop of a relativistic region of her conceptual profile.

Student A15

Similarly, also talking about the questions dealing with space contraction during the interview, student A15 states that “speed can distort the distance”, as she remembers an animated gif of a rocket, which was used on slides in class during activities:

[16:11] A15: Yes, because after being seen in class, we saw that speed can distort the distance, then.

E: And when you answered here in the post-test, what did you remember to mark that answer?

A15: I do not remember exactly what it was, but you showed a slide that was distorted, I think. I don't know if it was a rocket, what it was. [...] That, as you moved [#NAV2 16:41], the little thing it distorted itself like that.

As student A15 said, “speed can distort the distance”, which suggests that she considered the changes in space as real. This acceptance of these changes indicates the existence of a relativistic region in her conceptual profile of reference frame.

Figure 3. The dynamic gesture #NAV2 performed by student A15.

Moreover, this student performed the dynamic depictive gesture #NAV2 when remembered of a gif used in slides during classes. This gesture is evidence of the construction of an internal resource, a dynamical mental image by the interaction with a hypercultural mediation which helped the student to comprehend the theory.

Student A18

Student A18 also showed evidence of the development of the relativistic zone of conceptual profile. Talking about the questions during interview, he stated that “the higher the speed, the shorter the distance will be”, indicating the understanding of the contraction of space as a real phenomenon:

[19:27] A18: [...] That the speed is high, so the higher the speed, the shorter the distance will be.

E: So, in which of the two cases (50 km/h and 0.7c) would be the shortest distance?

A18: In both, I think ... Ah, what would be smaller, in question 3 (0.7c) because it is faster.

E: [...] What if it was a speed of 0.2c, for example?

A18: Then it would be between (questions) 1 and 3, I think.

E: And do you imagine that?

A18: Yes, I imagine [#NAV4 20:09] the path [travelled distance] literally getting smaller you know, as if it were in the gif, but then the path and not the spaceship, right.

This student also presented evidence of a complete understanding when demonstrated to comprehend the gradual relation between the speed and the changes in space saying that for a speed of 0.2c the measured distance “would be between (questions) 1 and 3”. This complete understanding and the acceptance of the space contraction indicate the existence of a relativistic region on is conceptual profile.

Figure 4. The dynamic gesture #NAV4 performed by student A18.

Moreover, he performed the dynamical depictive gesture #NAV4, remembering the same animated gif used in slides that student A15 also remembered:

[17:32] A18: So, I remembered the slides. I remember that there was a spaceship and all. What impressed me the most was that the spaceship was [#NAV4 17:50] decreasing in... And I believe that I have thought on it, because so [NAV4 18:14] its size decrease how faster it was. So, the faster it (truck of question) was, the smaller the path would be.

This gesture indicates the existence of an internal resource, a dynamical mental image, developed by the interaction with *hypercultural* mediation which helped him to comprehend the Special Relativity Theory and develop the relativistic zone in his conceptual profile of reference frame.

Student D23

Finally, student D23, also saw a relation between the phenomenon of space contraction with the speed of the reference frame, as well as showed signs of believing that the phenomenon is real, for example, when talking about his answers to the questions:

[15:24] D23: This one I already, I already agree, as it is at a higher speed [#DIS 15:30], it will arrive, it will contract a little, the length, and it will arrive faster than that he really thinks it's arrived.

E: What if the speed there instead of 0.7c, for example, was 0.9c? Was it going to change anything?

D23: Only the length, right. It was going to be [#DIS 15:50], it was going to be one, less length was going to be like [#DIS 15:54], it was going to increase the length, that is, it was going to increase the ... The distance, the distance was going to decrease, even more than he thought he really is. I don't know if it was clear.

Figure 5. The dynamic gesture #DIS performed by student D23.

Despite of showing some difficulty in expressing himself, the student treated the changes in space as real, saying that length “will contract a little”. This suggests he could develop the new relativistic region in his conceptual profile of reference frame.

He also performed a dynamical depictive gesture of approximating both hands, showing he has an internal resource, a dynamical mental image, which helped him to comprehend the situation. Even though, the student didn't mention the mediations used during activities, his gesture is very similar to the gestures performed by the other students.

CONCLUSION

The present research aimed to investigate the development of the relativistic zone in the conceptual profile (Mortimer, 1995) of reference frame of third year high school students dealing with the Special Relativity Theory (STR). Therefore, activities involving STR and contemplating the four levels of mediations according to Cognitive Networks Mediation Theory (Souza et al., 2012) were developed, as well as individual interviews with students.

Of the four students presented in this study, three said they remembered a rocket/spaceship present as an animated gif in one of the slides used in class. Also, the four students performed similar gestures, indicating that they have similar internal resources – mental images – that also seems to have not only from the animated gif as their only source, but also very similar to the computer simulation used to deal with the space contraction.

Answering the research question, the excerpts from the interviews and the gestures performed by students are indications that the use of different mediations, especially *hypercultural* ones, may have facilitated the development of internal resources, mental images, which helped the comprehension of the theory and the construction of a new zone of their conceptual profile of reference frame, apparently the relativistic one.

So, the use of the four mediations according to the CNMT, highlighting *hypercultural* mediation through computer simulations and animated gifs, proved to be a valid resource to facilitate the construction of new zones in the conceptual profile of reference frame, with indications that it is the relativistic zone of the profile. Therefore, we would recommend using the same type of resource with other subjects of Modern Physics, so to trigger the development of the corresponding (new) zone of conceptual profile to the many Modern Physics main concepts.

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